

High-resolution data, not model flexibility, drive accurate predictions of European winter storm damage

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Abstract

Winter storms are among Europe's costliest natural hazards, yet models that predict their damage remain scarce due to a lack of granular damage data. This has also hindered assessments of whether flexible machine-learning methods and novel, high-resolution hazard and exposure data improve predictive performance. We address this gap by applying three increasingly flexible model classes—generalised linear models, generalised additive models and XGBoost—to a unique insurance dataset containing approximately one million residential building insurance policies in force during nine winter storms in the Netherlands (9.4 million policy-storm observations in total). Using leave-one-storm-out cross-validation and an external extrapolation test, we evaluate out-of-sample residential building damage prediction across nested feature sets comprising high-resolution wind gusts, precipitation, atmospheric thermodynamic state variables (air pressure, air temperature and relative humidity), building characteristics and location effects. Feature selection affects prediction accuracy more than model class, and once informative features are included, models with different levels of flexibility and interpretability perform similarly. We therefore find no clear trade-off between interpretability and predictive performance. The best models achieve near-zero aggregate bias and an average absolute storm-level error below 38%, with errors largely attributable to uncaptured damage-relevant information. Relative to an open-source European wind-damage benchmark, our portfolio-calibrated approach reduces storm-level prediction errors by about 90%, demonstrating the value of tailored calibration over generic damage models. Future efforts to improve these models should prioritise the collection of relevant, high-resolution damage and feature data, especially when predicting damage from extreme winter storms.

Introduction

European winter storms are extratropical cyclones that can generate strong wind gusts and heavy precipitation across large parts of Europe for several consecutive days (Ulbrich et al., 2009). They are among the most hazardous and costly meteorological events in Europe, with single events capable of causing casualties and damage amounting to billions of euros (Cusack, 2023). Accurately predicting this damage is therefore key to insurance pricing (Grossi et al., 2005) and claims reserving (Gao and Shi, 2025), climate change policy development (Schwierz et al., 2010) and disaster preparedness planning (Merz et al., 2020). Climate change heightens the importance of accurate damage prediction, as it may weaken or completely halt the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (Portmann et al., 2026; van Westen and Dijkstra, 2026; Xing et al., 2026), which can increase the frequency and intensity of European winter storms (Jacob et al., 2005; van Westen and Baatsen, 2025).

Winter storm damage is typically quantified using the natural catastrophe modelling framework (Foote et al., 2017), which combines (i) a hazard module that describes the frequency and intensity of a peril, (ii) an exposure module that represents the spatial distribution and characteristics of assets, and (iii) a vulnerability module that predicts damage to assets based on the hazard's intensity and the assets' characteristics. The vulnerability module is especially influential in this framework because damage predictions adjust proportionally to changes in this module, while this can be less than proportional for changes in the hazard and exposure modules. However, empirically grounded vulnerability modules for European winter storms remain scarce in the literature (Koks and Haer, 2020), largely because high-resolution, accurate and consistent damage observations are rarely available in large quantities (Moemken et al., 2024).

The available vulnerability modules are typically calibrated using damage data that are either aggregated (Dorland et al., 1999; Kława and Ulbrich, 2003; Fonseca-Cerda et al., 2026), granular but based on expert judgement (Feuerstein et al., 2011), or accurate but limited to small samples (Khanduri and Morrow, 2003). Together, these limitations can reduce prediction accuracy, as aggregating data obscures variation and can bias the estimated hazard-damage relationship (Bryant et al., 2025), while expert judgement and small samples can limit the reliability and generalisability of vulnerability modules. In addition, winter storm damage predictions usually depend solely on wind speed, which serves as a hazard-intensity proxy (Gliksman et al., 2023). However, damage is also influenced by other drivers and moderating factors, including precipitation and building characteristics (van Ederen et al., 2025). Moreover, these relationships are often non-linear, and may include interaction effects that influence damage in complex ways (Trojand et al., 2025). Nevertheless, winter storm damage is often modelled using parametric functions that impose restrictive functional forms (Prahl et al., 2015) and without considering interactions.

Owing to the lack of damage data, it remains unclear whether flexible machine-learning methods combined with high-resolution, extensive hazard and exposure data can improve the damage predictions from a winter storm vulnerability module.

We address this gap by leveraging a unique, high-quality insurance dataset from a large Dutch financial conglomerate, containing approximately one million residential building insurance policies in force per winter storm, across nine storms that affected the Netherlands between 2017 and 2021. Pooling across winter storms yields around 9.4 million observations, which we refer to hereafter as policy-storm observations. The insurance data contain policyholder information, claims and building characteristics at the residential building level. Together, the storms resulted in around 55,000 residential building claims, corresponding to a total claimed amount of approximately €136 million in 2025 price levels. To capture the damage-driving winter storm dynamics, we augment the insurance data with novel, highly granular meteorological data: in addition to the commonly used wind gust speed, we include the 24-hour cumulative precipitation level, and are the first to consider atmospheric

thermodynamic state variables representing the daily mean air pressure, air temperature, and relative humidity, as well as their daily changes (Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2022). This allows us to test whether these atmospheric thermodynamic state variables capture damage-driving mechanisms that are not represented by conventional features, such as the possibility that denser air is more damaging.

We construct nested model specifications by progressively incorporating the meteorological features, building characteristics and location effects, and estimate each specification with three model classes that differ in their flexibility and interpretability. Generalised linear models (GLMs) represent our least flexible functional form, but offer transparent, coefficient-based interpretation (Nelder and Wedderburn, 1972). Generalised additive models (GAMs) retain an interpretable structure while allowing for more intricate non-linear effects through data-driven smooths, although interactions generally have to be specified manually (Hastie and Tibshirani, 1986). Finally, we are the first to apply XGBoost (XGB) to European winter storm damage modelling. XGB is an optimised gradient-boosted tree method (Friedman, 2001; Chen and Guestrin, 2016) and represents the most flexible model class in our comparison. Unlike the GLM and GAM, XGB can learn non-linearities and interactions automatically from the data, although interpreting XGB is more involved. Comparing these model class and specification combinations allows us to assess whether predictions of residential building damage from winter storms improve through greater model flexibility, improved input features, or both. It also allows us to examine whether any predictive gains come at the cost of reduced model interpretability, a key concern in explanation-sensitive applications such as insurance (Rudin, 2019).

Following the natural catastrophe modelling framework and terminology, our vulnerability module predicts the expected damage as the product of two separately estimated components: (i) a chance-of-loss model for predicting the probability of being damaged by a winter storm and (ii) a conditional-vulnerability model for predicting the damage ratio, given that damage occurred. The damage ratio measures damage relative to the object's reconstruction value. We estimate both components with every model class and specification combination described above, allowing us to assess separately how model flexibility and input features affect chance of loss, conditional damage ratio and expected damage predictions.

We assess predictive performance on unseen winter storms using a nested leave-one-storm-out cross-validation framework. In each outer fold, one complete winter storm is withheld as an unseen test event, while all model fitting and hyperparameter tuning are performed exclusively on the remaining storms in the inner loop. This design reduces the risk of overstating predictive performance on unseen winter storms, since observations from the same storm may contain event-specific information that could leak into the evaluation if these observations were split across training and test sets. It also reflects the typical application setting: generalising to future winter storms. In addition to the cross-validation analyses, we assess the extrapolation capabilities of our vulnerability module using an extreme winter storm and compare our prediction performance to an open-source European wind-damage benchmark.

Results

Expected damage

Table 1 presents the out-of-sample performance of the expected damage predictions for all model-class and specification combinations. For each policy-storm observation, expected damage is computed as the predicted chance of loss multiplied by the predicted conditional damage ratio and the associated reconstruction value. The chance of loss and conditional damage ratio predictions for each policy-storm observation stem from the chance-of-loss and conditional-vulnerability models, respectively. The policy-storm-level predictions are summed within each winter storm to obtain storm-level predictions for the expected damage, number of damaged buildings and conditional damage. The results for the chance-of-loss and conditional-vulnerability model performance are reported in Tables 2 and 3. The conditional-vulnerability model is evaluated on observations with damage, and in terms of damage rather than damage ratio, with damage computed as the predicted damage ratio multiplied by the associated reconstruction value.

In Tables 1-3, we report signed mean bias error (MBE) in the top rows, defined as the percentage difference between the total predicted and total observed values across all winter storms. This metric measures model calibration, where negative values denote underprediction and positive values denote overprediction. We report the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) in the bottom rows, which averages the absolute storm-level percentage errors, as a metric for storm-level predictive accuracy. All storm-level results are provided in Supplementary Tables S4-6. The Methods sections *Vulnerability module* and *Aggregation and out-of-sample evaluation metrics* provide further details on the derivation of expected damage from the chance-of-loss and conditional-vulnerability models, and on the aggregation formulas and performance metrics used for out-of-sample evaluation, respectively.

Table 1. Out-of-sample performance of the expected damage predictions. The top rows report signed mean bias error (MBE), defined as the percentage difference between total predicted and total observed damage across all winter storms. The bottom rows report mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), defined as the average absolute storm-level percentage error. The model specification abbreviations are: W for maximum wind gust; B for building characteristics; L for two-digit postal code location effects; P24 for 24-hour precipitation; TSm for daily mean of the thermodynamic state variables; and TSd for daily changes in the thermodynamic state variables. IO is the intercept-only benchmark.

Model	IO	W	W+B	W+B+L	W+B+L+P24	W+B+L+P24+TSm	W+B+L+P24+TSd
MBE							
IO	-0.42%						
GLM		-1.33%	1.71%	1.51%	4.27%	3.62%	58.07%
GAM		-2.90%	1.52%	1.22%	-2.86%	8.35%	-14.35%
XGB		-2.67%	0.60%	0.23%	-2.88%	36.18%	-4.81%
MAPE							
IO	62.70%						
GLM		40.11%	41.09%	37.32%	43.05%	59.63%	76.48%
GAM		40.61%	43.39%	37.79%	37.84%	61.90%	61.42%
XGB		40.16%	40.85%	37.71%	38.64%	154.91%	42.63%

The best expected damage predictions stem from a model specification that combines wind gusts, building characteristics, and two-digit postal-code location effects, which likely capture unobserved building and environmental characteristics. Within this specification, XGB achieves the lowest aggregate bias (MBE = 0.23%), whereas the GLM achieves the lowest storm-level error (MAPE = 37.32%). Nevertheless, predictive accuracy differs only marginally between the model classes of this best feature set.

Across all model class and specification combinations, the variation in predictive performance is substantially larger: the MBE ranges from -14.35% to 58.07%, and MAPE from 37.32% to 154.91%. These differences are primarily driven by model specification rather than by model class, suggesting that successful winter storm damage prediction depends more on the selected features than on the type of model applied. For example, the largest performance deterioration occurs when additional thermodynamic state variables are added to the wind gust, building characteristics and location effects specification, indicating that these variables do not provide a robust out-of-sample signal and instead induce overfitting.

The contrast between near-zero aggregate bias (MBE) and sizeable storm-level errors (MAPE) is central to the interpretation of the results. This unexplained damage variation at the storm level can be driven by data (e.g. uncaptured damage-relevant information), the model (e.g. misspecified relationships), or both. Four auxiliary cross-validation analyses that relax the strict nested leave-one-storm-out design support the first explanation. Two single-storm designs split observations per winter storm into training and test sets, either randomly or by location. A third design pooled observations from all cross-validation winter storms and split them into training and test sets at random. A fourth design trained the models on the usual outer training storms, recalibrated them on a small subset of the held-out test storm, and evaluated them on the remaining observations from that storm. In all cross-validation analyses, MAPE approached zero, suggesting that much of the error in the leave-one-storm-out cross-validation reflects information not captured by the available features, rather than model deficiencies.

These findings further support the idea that the observed unexplained damage variation can, conceptually, be described by a storm-level random effect that represents the aggregate influence of uncaptured factors. This storm-level random effect shifts the intercept, feature effects, or both in the damage model for the winter storm being predicted. Finding a low MBE suggests that such positive and negative storm-level random effects can cancel when predictions are aggregated over multiple storms, provided that the model is well-calibrated and the training sample is representative for the population. This result is important for operational use, as it implies that damage predictions over multiple winter storms are more accurate than those for single events due to the presence of storm-level random effects. For instance, insurance premiums based on damage estimates from multiple simulated winter storms may therefore be less uncertain than damage predictions used in stress tests of individual storms, assuming no additional uncertainty in storm probabilities is considered.

Figure 1. Spatial distribution of hazard, exposure, damage, and PC2-level damage percentage prediction error for the 9 February 2020 winter storm. a) Maximum wind gust per PC5; b) aggregate reconstruction value (portfolio exposure) per PC2; c) observed total damage per PC5; d) observed chance of loss per PC2; e) observed mean conditional damage ratio per PC2. f) GLM, g) GAM and h) XGB damage percentage prediction errors per PC2 for the model specification with wind gusts, building characteristics and location effects. The error metric is calculated as $100 \times (\text{PC2-level predicted total damage} - \text{PC2-level observed total damage}) / \text{PC2-level observed total damage}$. Negative values indicate underprediction and positive values indicate overprediction. PC2 and PC5 denote postal code aggregation levels based on the first two and first five characters of the Dutch postal code.

Figure 1 depicts the spatial distribution of hazard, exposure, damage and PC2-level damage percentage prediction error for the 9 February 2020 winter storm. Figure 1a shows a clear spatial gradient in wind gust intensity, with the highest wind gust speeds in the north-western Netherlands and the lowest in the south-east. Portfolio exposure, measured by aggregate reconstruction value, shows the opposite pattern, with higher exposure in the south than in the north (Figure 1b). The observed chance of loss and conditional damage ratio closely follow the hazard footprint, as areas exposed to stronger gusts generally show higher values (Figures 1d, e). By contrast, the aggregate PC5-level damage is relatively evenly distributed across the country (Figure 1c), with limited differences between areas exposed to the highest and lowest gusts. This pattern reflects the damage decomposition into chance of loss, conditional damage ratio and reconstruction value: although the south experienced lower wind intensities, its higher exposure compensated for the lower hazard, resulting in aggregate damage comparable to that in the less exposed but more severely affected north.

Figures 1f-h show that the spatial distribution of the damage prediction errors is highly similar across models. Moreover, all models underestimate damage in areas with higher wind gusts and overestimate damage in areas with lower wind gusts for this winter storm. This pattern is consistent with shrinkage toward the mean along the wind-gust dimension: predictions are compressed toward the average damage level along the wind-gust gradient, leading to underprediction at the highest wind gusts and overprediction at the lowest wind gusts. The close alignment between wind intensity and prediction errors suggests that this gravitation towards average damage is the dominant bias for this winter storm, while error patterns linked to building characteristics, location effects or uncaptured factors appear less pronounced.

The chance-of-loss and conditional-vulnerability models

Table 2. Out-of-sample chance-of-loss model performance. The top rows report signed mean bias error (MBE), defined as the percentage difference between the total predicted and total observed number of damaged residential buildings across all winter storms. The bottom rows report mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), defined as the average absolute storm-level percentage error in the predicted number of damaged residential buildings. The model specification abbreviations are: W for maximum wind gust; B for building characteristics; L for two-digit postal code location effects; P24 for 24-hour precipitation; TSm for daily mean of the thermodynamic state variables; and TSd for daily changes in the thermodynamic state variables. IO is the intercept-only benchmark.

Model	IO	W	W+B	W+B+L	W+B+L+P24	W+B+L+P24+TSm	W+B+L+P24+TSd
MBE							
IO	-0.02%						
GLM		-1.07%	-1.00%	-1.56%	0.84%	1.22%	34.01%
GAM		-2.40%	-1.92%	-2.07%	-5.80%	6.20%	-16.80%
XGB		-1.80%	-2.69%	-2.71%	-4.88%	31.35%	-7.22%
MAPE							
IO	47.29%						
GLM		30.28%	29.79%	24.68%	28.59%	39.50%	46.80%
GAM		30.94%	31.62%	26.71%	27.22%	43.68%	46.00%
XGB		31.28%	30.00%	27.58%	27.76%	110.98%	31.13%

Table 3. Out-of-sample conditional-vulnerability model performance. The conditional-vulnerability model is evaluated on observations with damage, and in terms of damage rather than damage ratio, with damage computed as the predicted damage ratio multiplied by the associated reconstruction value. The top rows report signed mean bias error (MBE), defined as the percentage difference between total predicted and total observed conditional damage across all winter storms. The bottom rows report mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), defined as the average absolute storm-level percentage error in conditional damage. The model specification abbreviations are: W for maximum wind gust; B for building characteristics; L for two-digit postal code location effects; P24 for 24-hour precipitation; TSm for daily mean of the thermodynamic state variables; and TSd for daily changes in the thermodynamic state variables. IO is the intercept-only benchmark.

Model	IO	W	W+B	W+B+L	W+B+L+P24	W+B+L+P24+TSm	W+B+L+P24+TSd
MBE							
IO	11.01%						
GLM		13.22%	4.61%	4.38%	4.68%	2.75%	12.55%
GAM		13.07%	4.01%	3.74%	3.96%	2.28%	7.22%
XGB		12.66%	3.53%	2.93%	2.62%	2.10%	5.61%
MAPE							
IO	15.93%						
GLM		16.83%	12.86%	12.68%	13.57%	16.93%	18.27%
GAM		16.73%	12.40%	12.20%	11.63%	16.42%	14.88%
XGB		16.07%	11.45%	11.28%	11.13%	18.08%	15.20%

Among the feature-based chance-of-loss models, the GLM including wind gusts, building characteristics, location effects and 24-hour precipitation achieved the lowest absolute MBE (0.84%). The GLM with wind gusts, building characteristics and location effects achieved the lowest MAPE (24.68%). For the conditional-vulnerability models, the XGB with wind gusts, building characteristics, location effects and daily mean thermodynamic state variables yielded the lowest absolute MBE (2.10%), whereas XGB with wind gusts, building characteristics, location effects and 24-hour precipitation achieved the lowest MAPE (11.13%).

Across most model-class and specification combinations, chance-of-loss models underpredict the number of damaged residential buildings, whereas conditional-vulnerability models overpredict conditional damage. The two components also exhibit distinct error profiles: chance-of-loss models generally have lower bias but higher storm-level errors than conditional-vulnerability models. The larger conditional-vulnerability model bias may reflect its smaller training sample, as conditional-vulnerability models are estimated only on damaged observations, whereas chance-of-loss models are estimated on the full residential building insurance portfolios. By contrast, the higher storm-level errors of the chance-of-loss models suggest that storm-level random effects influence the damage-occurrence process more strongly than the damage-severity process. Non-zero storm-level errors for both the chance-of-loss and conditional-vulnerability models are consistent with uncaptured storm-specific effects in both components. However, a storm-level random effect of a given magnitude is expected to have a larger effect on the damage-occurrence process because the chance-of-loss model represents a threshold-exceedance process, whereas the conditional-vulnerability model represents a post-threshold intensity process: in the chance-of-loss model, such a random effect can both shift the wind gust threshold at which buildings begin to incur damage and alter the predictions of buildings already above that threshold. For example, a positive storm-level random effect could lower the effective damage threshold from 20 m/s to 19 m/s, generating non-zero chance-of-loss predictions for buildings exposed to 19-20 m/s wind gusts while also increasing the predictions for buildings exposed to wind gusts above 20 m/s. The conditional-vulnerability model is less influenced by a similar random effect because it affects only the damaged buildings. Hence, a comparable random effect can induce larger storm-level prediction errors in chance-of-loss models than in conditional-vulnerability models.

Because expected damage is the product of the building-level chance-of-loss and conditional-vulnerability model predictions, errors in the two components can either reinforce or offset one another. When component errors have the same sign, expected damage errors tend to compound; when they have opposite signs, they may partly cancel. However, the expected damage error cannot be inferred directly from the aggregate chance-of-loss and conditional-vulnerability model errors in Tables 2 and 3, because it depends on how both errors are distributed across buildings. The wind-only specifications illustrate this point: although the chance-of-loss and conditional-vulnerability models have aggregate MBEs with opposite signs, the expected damage MBE does not reflect simple cancellation, but is more negative than the chance-of-loss MBE alone.

An exact attribution of expected damage error to either component is not possible, because true latent chance-of-loss and conditional-damage values are unobserved. Nevertheless, two simplified diagnostic perspectives can guide recommendations on which model component to prioritise for improvement. If the chance-of-loss model were assumed to classify damaged buildings perfectly, that is, chance of loss equals 1 for damaged buildings and 0 for non-damaged buildings, then the expected damage MBE and MAPE attributable to the conditional-vulnerability model would match the MBE and MAPE of the conditional-vulnerability model. Conversely, if the conditional-vulnerability model were assumed to predict conditional damage perfectly, and errors relative to the true latent chance of loss were proportional across buildings, then the expected damage MBE and MAPE attributable to the chance-of-loss model would match the MBE and MAPE of the chance-of-loss model. Under these assumptions, storm-level expected damage accuracy is most likely to improve through better chance-of-loss models, because their MAPE is structurally higher. Aggregate expected damage bias, in contrast, is most likely to improve through better conditional-vulnerability models, because their MBE is structurally higher.

To complement the aggregate evaluation metrics, Supplementary Figures S1 and S2 report insured-object-level diagnostics for the chance-of-loss and conditional-vulnerability models under the specification with wind gusts, building characteristics and location effects. For the GLM, GAM and XGB chance-of-loss models, out-of-sample predictions are evaluated using calibration curves. Across all model classes, these curves remain close to the perfect-calibration line over the main mass of the prediction distribution, indicating that insured-object-level predictions are well calibrated for most buildings. The main deviation occurs in the upper tail, where the calibration curves lie below the diagonal, indicating overprediction of the highest predicted chances of loss, especially for XGB.

For the GLM, GAM and XGB conditional-vulnerability models, out-of-sample predictions of the conditional damage ratio are evaluated using residual diagnostics. The LOWESS smooths of the conditional damage ratio residuals remain close to zero over the main mass of the prediction distribution for all model classes, indicating that mean predictions are well centred over most of the conditional damage ratio range. The GLM and GAM smooth residual curves turn upward at the highest predicted conditional damage ratios, indicating underprediction for some observations in this upper tail. XGB produces a wider range of predicted values, suggesting that it better differentiates observations with higher conditional damage ratios, while its smooth residual curve remains closer to zero across most of this range.

Overall, these diagnostics indicate that, under the specification with wind gusts, building characteristics and location effects, the chance-of-loss models are broadly well calibrated and the conditional-vulnerability models are generally well centred at the insured-object level. This is consistent with the low MBEs observed for the same specification in Tables 1–3. Moreover, the diagnostics suggest that the storm-level errors do not reflect a global miscalibration of insured-object-level predictions, but are instead compatible with storm-level random effects that can partly offset when predictions are aggregated across multiple storms.

In the next subsections, we examine what underlies the success of the best-performing models along the two dimensions that can be tested with our research design. We first assess the contribution of model specification, using performance differences across feature sets. We then evaluate the importance of non-linearities and interactions, using performance differences across model classes.

Model specification

Comparisons across feature sets show that informative features are essential for out-of-sample expected damage prediction: most feature-based models outperform the IO benchmark. The best expected damage predictions combine maximum wind gusts, building characteristics and location effects. Including the latter two in winter storm damage models is less common in the literature (Heneka and Ruck, 2008), yet both contribute substantially to the prediction accuracy in our study. The effects of these features in the chance-of-loss and conditional-vulnerability models for the GLM and GAM classes are depicted in Figures S3-6 in the Supplement. Figures S7-8 show the global SHAP feature importance and the SHAP beeswarm summary for local explanations for the chance-of-loss and conditional-vulnerability models. These figures indicate that feature effects are broadly consistent across model classes, with the GAM and XGB representing more intricate non-linear relationships, and XGB further extending this flexibility by learning interactions from the data. Figures S3-6 also highlight that the estimated effects are stable across the cross-validation training samples, supporting the interpretation that the models are capturing persistent signal rather than fold-specific noise.

Meteorological features

Consistent with previous literature (Fonseca-Cerda et al., 2025), our results confirm that wind gust speed is the dominant meteorological predictor of winter-storm-induced residential building damage. We find that adding 24-hour precipitation improves the prediction accuracy of the chance of loss and conditional damage for some model classes, but not of the expected damage predictions. This contrasts with recent evidence by van Ederen et al. (2025) that precipitation dynamics can add predictive value. A plausible explanation is that the storms in the present sample contained comparatively little precipitation, making omitted-variable bias from precipitation less pronounced. Adding thermodynamic state variables - daily mean air pressure, air temperature and relative humidity, or daily changes in these variables - consistently reduces the expected damage prediction performance for all model classes, and often does so substantially. Component-level results lead to the same interpretation: these variables do not provide a robust damage signal beyond wind gust speed; instead they increase the scope for overfitting in both the most flexible and the most constrained model classes tested.

Building characteristics

Our building characteristics include the reconstruction value, number of floors, building age at the event and residential building type. Adding these features to the wind-only specification markedly improves conditional-vulnerability model performance and produces smaller, less uniform gains in the chance-of-loss models. Reconstruction value is positively related to the chance of loss but negatively related to conditional damage ratio. This sign difference is consistent with a two-component vulnerability module, as both are estimated separately and predict differing targets. Reconstruction value mainly reflects building size, implying that larger residential buildings may be more exposed to wind loads and therefore more likely to be damaged. At the same time, damage does not increase proportionally with reconstruction value, lowering the conditional damage ratio. Number of floors follows a similar pattern: taller buildings may face stronger wind gusts at greater elevation, increasing the chance of loss, while a smaller roof area (per unit of reconstruction value) may reduce the conditional damage ratio. Building age is positively related to both the chance of loss and the conditional damage ratio, plausibly reflecting lower construction quality in older buildings or wear and tear. Relative to terraced houses, detached, semi-detached and corner houses have a higher chance of loss, whereas apartments have a lower chance of loss. These differences likely reflect differences in wind exposure; for instance, wind can reach detached houses more directly due to the absence of adjacent structures. Building type has a weaker effect on the conditional damage ratio, although detached houses and apartments show higher damage than terraced houses.

Location effects

Location effects are represented as random effects in the GLM and GAM and as categorical variables in XGB. They correspond to 90 two-digit postal code (PC2) areas, with an average area of approximately 420 km². Adding location effects improves prediction accuracy across most model classes, for both the chance-of-loss and conditional-vulnerability models. The gains are considerably larger for the chance-of-loss models, possibly because the conditional-vulnerability model is calibrated only on damaged buildings: the smaller sample shrinks GLM and GAM random effects towards zero and leaves many XGB location categories weakly estimated. Nevertheless, the strong gains observed for the chance-of-loss models suggest that better-informed location effects could also substantially improve the conditional-vulnerability models. In the chance-of-loss models, location effects likely capture unobserved building and environmental characteristics, such as construction materials and spatial differences in wind exposure, with urban areas often offering greater shielding from strong wind gusts than rural areas.

Figure 2. Spatial distribution of location effects in the chance-of-loss models. Maps show the estimated two-digit postal code (PC2) location effects for the wind gust, building characteristics and location effects specification in the GLM, GAM and XGB chance-of-loss models on the log-odds scale. For the GLM and GAM, the depicted location effects are represented by the coefficients of the random-effects term, for XGB these reflect the average SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) attributions per two-digit postal code (Lundberg et al., 2020). Positive values indicate locations with a higher predicted chance of loss than the model baseline; negative values indicate a lower predicted chance of loss.

The location-effect maps for the chance-of-loss models in Figure 2 show similar spatial patterns across model classes. However, location effects become slightly smaller in magnitude as model flexibility increases from GLM to GAM. This suggests that the GAM, being more flexible, captures some of the signal via the other features that the GLM instead assigns to location effects. Although the XGB location effects are expressed on the log-odds scale, their absolute magnitudes should not be interpreted as directly comparable with the GLM and GAM location effects because the estimands differ. We therefore compare the XGB results with the GLM and GAM results qualitatively, focusing on signs and spatial ranking rather than exact effect sizes. On this basis, all three model classes show a similar spatial pattern: two-digit postal code areas in northern and western parts of the Netherlands tend to contribute negatively to the predicted chance of loss, whereas southern and eastern areas tend to contribute positively. This pattern is consistent with building-code-driven adaptation in coastal areas through Dutch wind-load provisions (Nederlands Normalisatie-instituut, 2026), which classify coastal and large open-water areas as the highest wind-load region. The pattern may further reflect the higher degree of urbanisation in the west, which provides more wind shelter.

Non-linearities

We evaluate whether non-linearities are necessary for accurately predicting winter storm damage by comparing the predictive performance of all model classes with the wind gust, building characteristics, and location effects specification. Our results indicate that the winter storm damage process is characterised by numerous non-linear relationships. Figure 3 illustrates this by showing how both the chance of loss and the conditional damage ratio non-linearly relate to wind gust speeds across all model classes, holding the other features fixed at their mean or most frequently observed values. The predictions in Figure 3 are based on model fits using all eight cross-validation storms. Figures S9-10 in the Supplement depict these relationships per cross-validation training sample.

Figure 3. The relationship between chance of loss, conditional damage ratio and wind gust speed for all model classes. Panel (a) shows the predicted chance of loss; panel (b) shows the predicted conditional damage ratio. Predictions are from the wind gust, building characteristics, and location effects specification, evaluated over wind gust speed while holding all other features fixed at their mean values for continuous variables and most frequently observed values for categorical variables. The dashed vertical line marks the out-of-sample boundary at 35 m/s.

The chance-of-loss predictions from the GLM and GAM show a convex relationship with wind gust speed. In the GLM, this convexity is induced by the logit link and persists at higher wind gusts. In the more flexible GAM, the rate of increase becomes lower at high wind gusts. XGB follows the same increasing pattern up to 30 m/s, after which its predictions level off, a characteristic pattern of tree-based models at the edge of the feature space. The conditional damage ratio predictions of the GLM are almost linear over the plotted wind gust range, but would show slight convexity for larger extrapolations. The predictions from the GAM and XGB generally increase with wind gust speed, but they are not strictly monotonic because both exhibit a localised peak around 25 m/s. This peak is largely driven by the 9 February 2020 winter storm: as its high wind gust observations are associated with relatively low damage, this suppresses the damage predictions at higher wind speeds. The higher flexibility of GAM and XGB therefore allows them to capture this observed non-linearity, even though it is not necessarily physically consistent.

The feature effects plotted in Figures S3-6 also indicate prominent non-linear relationships between the continuous building-characteristic features and both the chance of loss and conditional damage ratio. Compared with the GLM, the GAM captures more intricate non-linearities. For instance, the relationship between reconstruction value and chance of loss is non-monotonic in the GAM. The feature effects in Figures S3-6 are shown on the model scale rather than on the prediction scale, corresponding to the log-odds of the chance of loss and the logit of the conditional damage ratio. Consequently, effects that appear linear on this scale translate into non-linear relationships after applying the inverse-link function. Such non-linear building-characteristic effects are often overlooked in the literature, where non-linearity is typically specified primarily for the wind-gust relationship.

Interactions

To assess the importance of interactions in the winter storm damage process, we examine how much of XGB's additional flexibility is used to learn interaction effects. For each feature, we decompose the SHAP value into a main effect and pairwise interaction contributions (Lundberg et al., 2020). SHAP values measure each feature's signed contribution to the model prediction relative to the baseline prediction, and mean absolute SHAP values are used here as a metric of global feature importance. We summarise the decomposition by reporting mean absolute main effects and mean absolute interaction remainders, defined as the contribution of pairwise interaction terms assigned to that feature. To avoid understating interactions, the interaction remainders are computed without allowing interaction partners to cancel one another. Figure 4 shows the main effects and interaction remainders decomposition for the chance-of-loss and conditional-vulnerability models with the wind gust, building characteristics and location effects specification. SHAP values are reported on the model scale, corresponding to the log-odds of the chance of loss and the logit of the conditional damage ratio. Supplementary Figures S11 and S12 show the pairwise interaction matrices for the chance-of-loss and conditional-vulnerability models, respectively.

Figure 4. XGB SHAP main-effect and interaction-remainder decomposition for the chance-of-loss and conditional-vulnerability models. The upper panel shows the chance-of-loss model and the lower panel shows the conditional-vulnerability model, both fitted on all eight cross-validation storms and with the wind gust, building characteristics and location effects specification. The dark segment denotes the mean absolute main effect, defined as the diagonal element of the SHAP pairwise interaction matrix. The light segment denotes the interaction remainder without partner cancellation, defined for each feature as the average of the sum of the absolute off-diagonal SHAP interaction terms assigned to that feature. Values for the chance-of-loss model are on the log-odds scale; values for the conditional-vulnerability model are on the logit scale.

Across both models, the decomposition shows that XGB relies mainly on main effects, with interaction effects adding smaller contributions. In the chance-of-loss model, wind gust is the dominant feature. Two-digit postal code and reconstruction value are next, followed by building age at event, residential building type and number of floors. The pairwise interaction matrix in Figure S11 shows that the largest interactions are wind gust with two-digit postal code, wind gust with reconstruction value, and reconstruction value with building age at event. These interactions are meaningful, but small compared with the corresponding main effects. They show that location effects and building characteristics modulate the wind-gust relationship rather than replacing wind gust as the main driver of the damage-occurrence process. In the conditional-vulnerability model, the feature importance hierarchy differs: reconstruction value is the dominant feature, followed by number of floors, wind gust, residential building type, building age at event and two-digit postal code. Figure S12 shows that the largest pairwise interactions are reconstruction value with residential building type and reconstruction value with number of floors. Thus, the damage-severity process is more dependent on building characteristics than the damage-occurrence process, and is also primarily driven by main effects.

The wind-gust SHAP decompositions in Figure 5 provide a local explanation of the same results. Whereas Figure 4 summarises main effects and interaction remainders globally, Figure 5 shows how the ordinary wind-gust SHAP value for each observation is composed of the wind-gust main effect and the signed interaction remainder across all interaction partners. If the ordinary SHAP dependence pattern closely matches the main-effect panel, the wind-gust relationship is mainly learned as a main effect; if the interaction-remainder panel contains a strong systematic pattern, interactions play an important role. For the colour scale, Figure 5 uses reconstruction value in the chance-of-loss model and building age at event in the conditional-vulnerability model, as these are the strongest continuous interaction partners of wind gust in the respective pairwise SHAP interaction matrices.

Figure 5. XGB SHAP decomposition of the wind-gust contribution in the chance-of-loss and conditional-vulnerability models. The upper panels show the decomposition for the chance-of-loss model and the lower panels for the conditional-vulnerability model, both fitted on all eight cross-validation storms and with the wind gust, building characteristics and location effects specification. Panel (a) shows the ordinary SHAP dependence plot for wind gust, panel (b) shows the wind-gust main effect, and panel (c) shows the wind-gust interaction remainder. The ordinary SHAP value equals the sum of the main effect and the interaction remainder. Each point represents an observation included in the SHAP calculation, and the grey histogram shows the empirical distribution of wind gusts. Colour indicates the strongest continuous pairwise interaction partner selected from the pairwise SHAP interaction matrix: reconstruction value for the chance-of-loss model and building age at event for the conditional-vulnerability model. SHAP values are displayed on the log-odds scale for the chance-of-loss model and on the logit scale for the conditional-vulnerability model.

In the chance-of-loss model, the wind-gust SHAP dependence plot is almost entirely reproduced by the wind-gust main effect, increasing from strongly negative contributions at low wind gusts to strongly positive contributions at high wind gusts. The interaction remainder varies locally by reconstruction value and other partners, but remains small and does not alter the overall monotonic wind-gust relationship. In the conditional-vulnerability model, wind gust has a weaker and less monotonic contribution. This pattern is again mainly reproduced by the wind-gust main effect, while the interaction remainder introduces only small local deviations.

Overall, the interaction analysis suggests that XGB's additional flexibility is used mainly to learn non-linear main effects, with interactions acting as secondary modifiers. This helps explain why XGB does not clearly improve expected damage prediction: interaction effects are present, but limited in absolute contribution, and therefore do not give XGB a clear advantage over the GLM and GAM specifications, which do not include interaction effects in this study.

Model flexibility, prediction performance and interpretability

Despite the importance of non-linear relationships and the presence of modulating interaction effects, the model class comparison shows that combining increasingly flexible chance-of-loss and conditional-vulnerability models does not improve the prediction accuracy of expected damage. For instance, the GLM combination performs approximately on par with the GAM and XGB combinations. In particular, the chance-of-loss model accuracy does not improve consistently with model flexibility, suggesting that the GLM link function, features and location effects already capture the main structure of the damage-occurrence process. In contrast, the conditional-vulnerability model accuracy improves with flexibility, indicating that the damage-severity process contains more intricate non-linearities and more influential interaction effects than the damage-occurrence process. The stronger conditional-vulnerability model performance of XGB suggests that a hybrid two-component vulnerability module may prove valuable. Suitable candidates could be the GLM chance-of-loss model and an XGB conditional-vulnerability model with the wind gust, building characteristics, and location effects specification, as both improve upon the other model classes' MBE and MAPE scores. Because expected damage errors cannot be inferred directly from aggregate component errors, this hybrid module should first be constructed and evaluated before any recommendation can be made.

The similar predictive performance of model classes with differing degrees of interpretability also suggests there is currently no clear trade-off between the two. Interpretability is important for users such as (re)insurers, who must be able to justify model use to regulators, customers and internal governance processes. However, the above conclusions are based on contemporaneous damage, building and meteorological data quality and granularity. Future improvements in data accuracy and granularity could reveal additional non-linearities and interactions that flexible, less interpretable methods can exploit. Conversely, our results may also be the first sign that the winter storm damage process is actually less complex than highly flexible models are capable of expressing.

Extrapolation to the 18 January 2018 winter storm

Extreme winter storms are particularly relevant for societal stakeholders, such as insurers, because such storms can generate large losses. As extreme-event damage data for model training are even scarcer, we assess the extrapolation capacity of all model classes within the best-performing model specification by predicting damage for the 18 January 2018 winter storm. This event was substantially more severe than the winter storms analysed in the cross-validation: it generated almost five times as many damaged buildings, and more than seven times the observed damage, as the largest event in the cross-validation sample. Table 4 reports the prediction errors of the chance of loss, conditional damage and expected damage from all model classes, using the wind gust, building characteristics and location effects specification, with the models fitted on all eight cross-validation storms.

Table 4. Extrapolation performance for the 18 January 2018 storm. Reported values denote storm-level prediction errors, calculated as percentage differences between aggregate model predictions and observations for the chance of loss, conditional damage, and expected damage. Positive values correspond to overprediction and negative values to underprediction.

Buildings in portfolio	Damaged buildings	Observed damage	
1,067,853	30,162	€85,484,652	
	Chance of loss	Conditional damage	Expected damage
IO	-89.63%	-15.82%	-92.47%
GLM	-67.41%	-19.45%	-74.84%
GAM	-69.17%	-22.11%	-76.69%
XGB	-74.85%	-25.73%	-81.78%

All models substantially underpredict the 18 January 2018 winter storm. The intercept-only benchmark is least suitable for this extrapolation task, because it can reproduce only the average chance of loss and conditional damage observed in the substantially less severe training storms. Among the feature-based models, the GLM underpredicts the least (-74.84%), followed by GAM (-76.69%) and XGB (-81.78%). The underprediction seems mainly driven by the chance-of-loss models: the GLM, GAM and XGB chance of loss errors are -67.41%, -69.17% and -74.85%, respectively, whereas the corresponding conditional-vulnerability model errors are considerably smaller in magnitude. The XGB performs worst among the feature-based models because its tree structure cannot extrapolate beyond the training data, as is also visible in the chance-of-loss plateau after wind gusts of 30 m/s in Figure 3.

These findings suggest that predictions become unreliable for winter storms far outside the hazard intensity range represented in the training data. This extrapolation test also suggests that model class cannot compensate for an absence of representative extreme events in the training data. For instance, models without the extrapolation limitations of XGB, such as the GLM and GAM, perform only marginally better in this setting.

These findings do not imply that all hazard intensity extrapolation is impossible. In the leave-one-storm-out cross-validation, the 9 February 2020 storm had about 50% more damaged buildings than the largest storm available in its training data, yet the GLM chance-of-loss model underpredicted it by only 8.95%. Consistent with the 18 January 2018 results, the GAM and XGB underestimate the 9 February 2020 storm more strongly. Thus, extrapolating to an event around 50% larger than the training maximum appears possible, whereas extrapolating to an event with a fivefold increase in damaged buildings exceeds the information contained in the training data.

Literature comparison

To evaluate our results relative to the existing literature, we benchmark the model class and specification combination that produced the best expected damage predictions against the open-source European wind-damage approach of Koks and Haer (2020), hereafter referred to as KH20. We match the Copernicus wind gust footprints used in that approach to our portfolios and apply their recalibrated vulnerability model, derived from Feuerstein et al. (2011), to our reconstruction value estimates. Unlike our two-component vulnerability module, Koks and Haer (2020) use a single expected-vulnerability model that combines the chance-of-loss and conditional-vulnerability models.

Table 5. Benchmark against Koks and Haer (2020). Storm-level comparison between observed residential building damage, predictions from the best-performing model in this study, and estimates based on KH20. The study's model is the GLM with the wind gust (W), building characteristics (B) and location effects (L) specification. For each winter storm, the table reports the number of buildings in the portfolio, the number of damaged buildings, observed damage, predicted damaged buildings, predicted conditional damage and expected damage, together with percentage prediction errors. Positive percentage differences indicate overprediction, negative values indicate underprediction. Signed MBE reports the percentage difference between the total predicted and total observed values across all winter storms, MAPE reports the average absolute winter-storm level percentage error.

Winter storm	Buildings in portfolio	Observed damaged buildings	Observed damage	GLM W + B + L						KH20	
				Predicted damaged buildings	% difference	Predicted conditional damage	% difference	Expected damage	% difference	Expected damage	% difference
18-1-2018	1,067,853	30,162	€85,484,652	9,829	-67.41%	€68,860,978	-19.45%	€21,504,608	-74.84%	€2,561,763	-97.00%
9-2-2020	1,028,953	6,049	€11,609,644	5,507	-8.95%	€13,945,261	20.12%	€12,546,828	8.07%	€66,311,644	471.18%
10-3-2019	1,040,244	3,921	€9,386,094	2,189	-44.18%	€8,803,905	-6.20%	€4,609,924	-50.89%	€15	-100.00%
3-1-2018	1,068,280	3,393	€7,882,052	3,202	-5.62%	€6,913,032	-12.29%	€6,582,129	-16.49%	€9,382,637	19.04%
23-2-2017	1,072,383	3,210	€6,676,547	2,928	-8.78%	€6,684,911	0.13%	€6,062,937	-9.19%	€ -	-100.00%
11-3-2021	1,024,003	2,451	€4,787,204	2,916	18.98%	€5,063,684	5.78%	€6,023,645	25.83%	€3,906	-99.92%
16-2-2020	1,029,050	2,225	€4,969,277	2,659	19.51%	€4,750,043	-4.41%	€5,632,479	13.35%	€5	-100.00%
23-2-2020	1,029,098	1,746	€2,828,088	2,730	56.36%	€3,553,269	25.64%	€5,810,024	105.44%	€ -	-100.00%
10-2-2020	1,029,029	1,379	€2,359,111	1,863	35.07%	€2,993,760	26.90%	€3,993,309	69.27%	€66,322,547	2,711.34%
Total	9,388,893	54,536	€135,982,670	33,823		€121,568,842		€72,765,882		€144,582,516	

	Predicted damaged buildings	Predicted conditional damage	Expected damage	Expected damage
MBE	-37.98%	-10.60%	-46.49%	6.32%
MAPE	29.43%	13.44%	41.49%	422.05%

Table 5 shows that the GLM substantially outperforms KH20 in terms of MAPE, which captures the average absolute storm-level prediction error. Except for the 3 January 2018 storm, KH20 either strongly overestimates or strongly underestimates expected damage. It also predicts no damage for the 23 February 2017 and 23 February 2020 storms because the Copernicus wind gust estimates do not exceed the 32 m/s damage threshold implied by the Feuerstein et al. (2011) vulnerability model. The near-zero MBE of KH20 is therefore misleading: it reflects cancellation between large errors of opposite sign rather than accurate aggregate damage predictions.

The performance gap indicates that winter storm vulnerability models have limited transferability across settings. Although vulnerability-model transferability has been discussed more extensively in the flood-damage literature (Wagenaar et al., 2018), our results show that it is equally relevant for winter storms. Vulnerability modules should therefore be calibrated to the portfolio of interest, with hazard, exposure and damage data kept consistent between calibration and prediction. The comparison also suggests that part of the performance difference arises because the Feuerstein et al.-based vulnerability model does not account for building characteristics or location effects, both of which improve prediction performance in our models.

The comparison further highlights the importance of highly granular hazard, exposure and damage data. Figure 1 shows substantial small-scale variation in wind gusts within the 9 February 2020 storm. The Copernicus hazard data used by Koks and Haer (2020) consist of model-generated 3-second gust footprints on a 0.04° grid, corresponding to approximately 4.4 km resolution and a grid-cell area about four times larger than the product used here. Spatially coarser hazard grids smooth sub-grid variation, which can introduce systematic prediction bias when vulnerability relationships are non-linear and hazard intensity varies substantially within grid cells. This is a direct implication of Jensen's inequality: $f(\mathbb{E}[Hazard]) \neq \mathbb{E}[f(Hazard)]$ for non-linear vulnerability model f . In this context, the inequality implies that a non-linear vulnerability model's predictions are inherently hazard scale-dependent: predictions differ when using aggregated hazard data compared with data at a more granular scale. Because damage occurs at the asset scale, and because we show that the hazard-impact relationship is non-linear, using spatially aggregated hazard data can reduce the accuracy of downstream damage estimates.

Granular damage observations are also important for vulnerability module calibration. Owing to the limited availability of high-resolution damage data, Koks and Haer (2020) recalibrated the Feuerstein et al. vulnerability model using aggregate country-storm damage estimates. Such aggregate totals contain no information on within-country heterogeneity and therefore cannot reliably identify effects that vary at finer spatial scales. For example, aggregate damage data cannot disentangle the direct effect of wind gust speed from elevated vulnerability due to, for instance, building characteristics. These effects can only be identified when damage variation is observed at the scale at which the relevant features vary.

Discussion

Our results suggest that accurate winter storm damage predictions do not necessarily require highly flexible vulnerability modelling. Instead, the largest gains in out-of-sample prediction performance for chance of loss, conditional damage ratio, and expected damage come from using the right features: wind gust, building characteristics, and location effects. Once the most informative features are included, enhanced model flexibility does not improve expected damage accuracy. A more fundamental explanation for these results may be that the predictive structure of winter storm damage is less complex than flexible machine-learning methods, such as XGBoost, allow for. This finding also has practical importance, as it suggests that less flexible but transparent and interpretable models can be used without loss of predictive performance. This is valuable when model-based decisions must be explainable, auditable, and defensible to regulators, customers, and internal stakeholders, for instance in an insurance setting.

We also identify an unresolved source of uncertainty in vulnerability modelling: unexplained storm-level damage variation arising from uncaptured damage-relevant information, which we conceptualise as storm-level random effects. We observe that predictions across multiple winter storms are more accurate than those for individual storms, suggesting that these storm-level random effects may average out for well-calibrated models. The extrapolation test reinforces and extends the central findings of our study: reliable damage predictions depend on adequate and representative training data; model-class choice has only limited influence when such data are lacking; and estimates for winter storms far outside the training domain should be treated with caution. This has important implications for climate change impact analyses, where damage estimates may require extrapolation to future winter storm conditions that are not well represented in historical training data (Little et al., 2023). Finally, the substantially better performance of our portfolio-calibrated vulnerability modules relative to an open-source European wind-damage approach underscores the limited transferability of generic vulnerability models and highlights the importance of consistent, portfolio-specific calibration.

Taken together, our findings provide several recommendations for developing next-generation winter storm vulnerability modules. Efforts to improve winter storm damage prediction should primarily focus on collecting damage data from more winter storms and improving the quality, granularity, and consistency of hazard and exposure data. As hazard data become more accurate and granular, including through next-generation climate-modelling efforts such as CMIP7 (Dunne et al., 2025), and exposure data become more comprehensive (Mühlhofer et al., 2024), we expect the predictive performance of vulnerability modules to improve further. Better data may also reveal whether more intricate non-linearities and complex interaction effects are present, creating the conditions under which flexible machine-learning methods can fully exploit these signals. Until such data become available, we encourage researchers to test other modern machine-learning methods such as explainable boosting machines (Lou et al., 2012, 2013; Nori et al., 2019), which combine flexible, data-driven shape functions with an additive structure and may therefore reduce bias relative to simpler models while limiting variance relative to less constrained methods.

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Methods

Data

The chance-of-loss and conditional-vulnerability models are developed using insurance data from a Dutch financial conglomerate, building data from the Dutch national register of addresses and buildings (BAG), and meteorological data from the Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute (KNMI), the Dutch national weather service. The main results are derived from the nested leave-one-storm-out cross-validation framework, using eight winter storms that affected the Netherlands on 23-02-2017, 03-01-2018, 10-03-2019, 09-02-2020, 10-02-2020, 16-02-2020, 23-02-2020, and 11-03-2021. A ninth, outlier winter storm on 18-01-2018 is reserved as an external extrapolation test, as it is substantially more severe than the cross-validation storms. For each winter storm, there were approximately 1 million residential building insurance policies in force in the portfolio. Combined over all winter storms, there are approximately 55,000 claims reported, equivalent to a total insured damage of around €136 million in 2025 price levels.

Insurance data

The insurance data contain residential building insurance information for the Netherlands at the insured-object level, i.e. the residence. The dataset includes policyholder information (e.g., address) and claim information (e.g., claim date and claim amount) for residential building damage. For each of the nine winter storm events, we construct an at-risk portfolio consisting of all residential building insurance policies that are in force on the event date. We then merge this portfolio with claim information from the event date to identify event-related damage. This yields an event-by-building sample in which most observations correspond to non-claims and a smaller set corresponds to claims. Filters are applied to isolate winter storm-related residential building claims on the event date. The full filter specification is documented in section S1 in the Supplement.

Claim amounts in the insurance data represent compensated damage net of any deductibles. To approximate ground-up damage (i.e., total damage prior to deductibles), we add an average deductible of €200 to claims for policyholders who are subject to a deductible.

Building characteristics data

We enrich the insurance data with publicly available residential building characteristics, which contain a broader set of features and are more consistent than the policyholder information at our disposal. We use the Dutch national basic registration of addresses and buildings (BAG). The BAG contains official information on all addresses and buildings in the Netherlands, including residential building characteristics. The following building characteristics are used, some of which are derived from the original BAG information: residential building type (terraced house, corner house, semi-detached house, detached house, and apartment), building age at winter storm event, surface of living area, surface of building footprint, and an approximation for the number of floors, i.e. surface living area/surface building footprint.

Based on these building characteristics, a reconstruction value is estimated using a method provided by the Dutch Association of Insurers. This reconstruction value approximates the cost of rebuilding the residential building according to current building codes. Section S2 in the Supplement provides details on the reconstruction-value methodology.

All monetary data (i.e., ground-up damage and reconstruction values) are converted to 2025 price levels. We construct a price index specifically for this purpose, and describe the underlying data sources and index-construction methodology in section S3 in the Supplement.

Meteorological data

Meteorological data are retrieved from the KNMI, the Dutch national weather service. We combine validated wind climatology datasets (Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut, 2018, 2019, 2022) with a radar-based, gauge-adjusted precipitation dataset (Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut, 2017) to describe winter storm dynamics. All variables are available as hourly time series per grid point in a domain covering the Netherlands. The wind climatology datasets range from 2008 up to and including 2021 and are provided at a horizontal resolution of 2.5 km. The precipitation dataset ranges from 2008 up to the present date and is provided at a horizontal resolution of 1 km.

Wind climatology data

The wind climatology datasets are produced by downscaling the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) ERA5 reanalysis using the numerical weather prediction model HARMONIE-AROME. The datasets comprise the Dutch Offshore Wind Atlas (DOWA), which ranges from 2008 up to and including 2017 (Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut, 2018), the DOWA extension for 2018 (Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut, 2019), and a further extension until 2021 named the Winds of the North Sea in 2050 (WINS50) (Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut, 2022). The wind-climatology datasets contain five meteorological variables with observations representing hourly means measured at 17 fixed height levels between 10 m and 600 m: wind speed (m/s), wind direction (degrees), air pressure (Pa), air temperature (K), and relative humidity (%). We use the hourly mean wind speed measured at 140 m as a proxy for the maximum 3-second wind gust in a 10-minute period at 10 m height (van den Brink, 2019).

Precipitation data

Hourly precipitation measurements are obtained from the KNMI climatological gauge-adjusted radar rainfall dataset (Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut, 2017). This dataset provides one-hour cumulative precipitation level (mm) over the land surface of the Netherlands, derived from composites of KNMI weather-radar reflectivities and adjusted using validated and complete rain-gauge observations from KNMI rain-gauge networks (Overeem et al., 2011; Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut, 2017). Following van Ederen et al. (2025), we use the 24-hour cumulative precipitation level as a hazard-intensity metric, which is derived as the sum of the 24 hourly precipitation levels on the event date.

Data preparations

The insurance data are matched to the BAG building characteristics data based on address. This combined dataset is then spatially matched to the gridded meteorological data by assigning each insured building the values from the meteorological grid cell whose centroid is closest to the centroid of the neighbourhood in which the building is located. Temporal matching is performed by retaining only the meteorological observations on the winter storm event date. For the atmospheric thermodynamic state variables, we compute their daily mean as the average of the 24 hourly measurements on the event date, and their daily changes as the difference between the maximum and minimum measurements. Tables 6 and 7 provide the descriptive statistics for the chance-of-loss and conditional-vulnerability models, respectively.

Table 6. Descriptive statistics for the chance-of-loss model. Summary statistics are calculated at the insured-object level for all observations used in the chance-of-loss model (n = 9,388,893). The damage indicator equals 1 if damage occurred and 0 otherwise. Reconstruction values are expressed in 2025 euros. Daily changes are maximum-minus-minimum values on the event date; relative humidity is reported as a percentage and relative-humidity changes as percentage points. Building-type shares are reported as sample proportions.

Variable	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Q25	Median	Q75	Max
Numerical variables							
Damage indicator	0.006	0.076	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.000
Maximum wind gust (m/s)	24.13	3.27	11.26	22.31	24.09	26.17	35.72
24-hour precipitation (mm)	12.20	7.19	0.00	6.54	11.40	16.57	40.68
Daily mean air pressure (Pa)	99,628	727	96,628	99,132	99,487	99,928	101,585
Daily mean air temperature (K)	280.95	1.90	275.66	279.94	281.16	281.88	285.56
Daily mean relative humidity (%)	82.46	4.13	71.80	79.97	83.07	85.39	93.14
Daily pressure change (Pa)	1,605	625	643	1,195	1,450	1,716	3,580
Daily temperature change (K)	5.52	1.32	1.30	4.57	5.36	6.40	9.48
Daily relative-humidity change (percentage points)	24.66	5.47	5.56	20.72	24.72	28.73	41.71
Reconstruction value (2025 EUR)	404,269	207,995	2,584	281,880	351,654	462,949	3,159,274
Number of floors	1.70	0.42	1.00	1.41	1.68	1.99	4.00
Building age at event (years)	48.26	35.63	0.00	25.00	42.00	60.00	1,016.00
Residential building type shares							
Building type	Share						
Terraced house	37.8%						
Detached house	27.9%						
Corner house	16.6%						
Semi-detached house	15.5%						
Apartment	2.2%						

Table 7. Descriptive statistics for the conditional-vulnerability model. Summary statistics are calculated at the insured-object level, and for observations with damage used in the conditional-vulnerability model (n = 54,536). The damage ratio is ground-up damage divided by reconstruction value and values greater than or equal to 1 are capped at 0.99. Ground-up damage and reconstruction values are expressed in 2025 euros. Daily changes are maximum-minus-minimum values on the event date; relative humidity is reported as a percentage and relative-humidity changes as percentage points. Building-type shares are reported as sample proportions.

Variable	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Q25	Median	Q75	Max
Numerical variables							
Damage ratio	0.0060	0.0132	0.0000	0.0018	0.0034	0.0064	0.9900
Ground-up damage (2025 EUR)	2,493	7,382	18	749	1,350	2,550	1,156,422
Maximum wind gust (m/s)	27.12	2.85	11.49	25.28	27.58	29.08	35.72
24-hour precipitation (mm)	10.15	5.08	0.00	6.75	9.74	12.22	40.49
Daily mean air pressure (Pa)	99,508	501	96,628	99,290	99,457	99,606	101,574
Daily mean air temperature (K)	279.45	2.08	275.67	277.72	278.55	281.34	285.52
Daily mean relative humidity (%)	83.45	2.95	72.07	82.16	83.58	85.42	92.27
Daily pressure change (Pa)	1,837	560	658	1,490	1,764	1,937	3,576
Daily temperature change (K)	6.53	1.50	1.92	5.34	6.69	7.83	9.48
Daily relative-humidity change (percentage points)	25.15	4.63	6.75	21.96	25.49	28.87	40.99
Reconstruction value (2025 EUR)	459,956	255,458	6,235	304,196	389,999	528,916	3,159,274
Number of floors	1.71	0.42	1.00	1.41	1.68	1.98	4.00
Building age at event (years)	51.44	38.64	0.00	26.00	45.00	68.00	670.00
Residential building type shares							
Building type	Share						
Detached house	35.3%						
Terraced house	29.2%						
Corner house	18.1%						
Semi-detached house	15.6%						
Apartment	1.7%						

Vulnerability module

Our vulnerability module predicts winter storm damage at the residential building level as the product of two separately estimated components: the chance-of-loss model and the conditional-vulnerability model. For building i and winter storm s , let D_{is} denote the ground-up damage amount, R_i the reconstruction value of the residential building, and x_{is} the vector of meteorological, building and location features.

We define the binary damage indicator as

$$Z_{is} = 1(D_{is} > 0)$$

and, for observations with damage, the conditional damage ratio is distributed as

$$Y_{is} \sim D_{is} / R_i \mid D_{is} > 0$$

with values greater than or equal to 1 capped at 0.99 so that $Y_{is} \in (0,1)$, as required for the Beta distribution.

The chance-of-loss model estimates

$$p_{is} = \Pr(Z_{is} = 1 \mid x_{is})$$

whereas the conditional-vulnerability model estimates

$$v_{is} = E(Y_{is} \mid Z_{is} = 1, x_{is})$$

The estimated expected damage for residential building i from winter storm s is therefore

$$\widehat{\mu}_{is} = \widehat{p}_{is} \widehat{v}_{is} R_i \tag{1}$$

where hats denote out-of-sample predicted values.

Both components of the vulnerability module are estimated with three model classes: generalised linear models, generalised additive models and XGBoost. The chance-of-loss model is fitted and evaluated on the full residential building insurance portfolios, whereas the conditional-vulnerability model is fitted and evaluated only on residential buildings with damage. All model classes are fitted with the same nested feature sets: the wind-only specification, the building specification additionally includes reconstruction value, building age at the event date, number of floors and residential building type. The location specification further adds two-digit postal code location effects. The meteorological extensions add 24-hour cumulative precipitation, daily mean thermodynamic state variables, or daily changes in thermodynamic state variables. The atmospheric thermodynamic state variables comprise air pressure, air temperature and relative humidity. Finally, we include an intercept-only benchmark, which predicts the training sample averages, allowing us to evaluate the predictive performance gains from including additional features.

Generalised linear models

We use generalised linear models as the main interpretable parametric specification (Nelder and Wedderburn, 1972). These models impose the least flexible functional form among the fitted model classes: feature effects are additive and linear on the link scale, and nonlinearity enters only through the link function. For the chance-of-loss model, we use a Bernoulli distribution with a logit link. For the conditional-vulnerability model, we use a Beta distribution with a logit link. Continuous features enter linearly, categorical features, such as building type, enter through indicator variables, and the two-digit postal code location effects enter as penalised random-effect terms. We do not specify interactions for this model class, and the models are applied using the R package *mgcv* (Wood, 2011, 2017), with the large-data GAM methods of Wood et al. (2015).

Generalised additive models

We use generalised additive models to test whether more intricate non-linear effects improve winter storm damage prediction while retaining an additive and interpretable structure (Hastie and Tibshirani, 1986). These models use the same response distributions and link functions as the generalised linear models: a Bernoulli distribution with a logit link for the chance-of-loss model and a Beta distribution with a logit link for the conditional-vulnerability model. Continuous features enter as penalised thin-plate regression splines, categorical features through indicator variables, and the two-digit postal code location effects enter as penalised random-effect terms. We tune the gamma parameter within the inner leave-one-storm-out cross-validation loop, considering candidate values of 1, 5, 10, 50 and 100. See section *Nested leave-one-storm-out cross-validation* for a description of the complete cross-validation framework. Increasing gamma strengthens the effective degrees-of-freedom penalty in smoothness selection, forcing smoother, less wiggly fits that can improve predictions by reducing overfitting. We do not specify interactions for this model class, and the models are applied using the R package *mgcv* (Wood, 2011, 2017), with the large-data GAM methods of Wood et al. (2015).

XGBoost

We use XGBoost as the most flexible model class, allowing intricate non-linear effects and complex interactions to be learned from the data rather than specified in advance (Chen and Guestrin, 2016). XGBoost is an optimised implementation of gradient-boosted decision trees (Friedman, 2001). It builds an ensemble of regression trees sequentially, with each new tree improving the current ensemble by reducing the task-specific prediction loss. Model complexity is controlled through tree-depth restrictions, shrinkage and regularisation of the leaf weights.

We fit XGBoost as a binary classifier for the chance-of-loss model and as a regression model for the conditional-vulnerability model. The chance-of-loss model uses a logistic binary-classification objective, and the conditional-vulnerability model uses a logistic regression objective. Unlike the generalised linear and generalised additive models, XGBoost does not require linear or additive feature effects. Non-linearities and interactions can arise through recursive partitioning of the feature space. We do not impose monotonicity or interaction constraints.

Hyperparameters are tuned within the inner leave-one-storm-out cross-validation loop. See section *Nested leave-one-storm-out cross-validation* for a description of the complete cross-validation framework. We tune the number of boosting iterations, maximum tree depth, and L1 and L2 regularisation. The same predefined search space and fixed parameters are used for both the chance-of-loss and conditional-vulnerability models. The full search space and fixed parameters are reported in Supplementary Table S3. The models are applied using the Python *xgboost* package (Chen and Guestrin, 2016).

Nested leave-one-storm-out cross-validation

The aim of this study is to assess the predictive performance of the different vulnerability modules on unseen winter storms. Because observations from the same winter storm may contain event-specific information, a random policy-storm-level split could overstate predictive performance relative to a setting in which the model is applied to entirely unseen winter storms. In such a split, observations from the same winter storm could be assigned to both the training and test sets, allowing storm-specific signals to leak into the evaluation. To reduce this risk and to reflect the typical operational prediction setting, we perform cross-validation at the winter-storm level. This design ensures that all observations from a given winter storm are assigned to the same fold.

Specifically, we apply a nested leave-one-storm-out (LOSO) cross-validation framework to fit and test the chance-of-loss models and the conditional-vulnerability models, using eight winter storms. Figure 6 depicts a schematic overview of this framework. In each outer fold, one winter storm is held out for final testing, while the remaining seven winter storms form the outer training set. Hyperparameter tuning for the GAM and XGB models is performed entirely within this outer training set, following an inner leave-one-storm-out cross-validation procedure. For each candidate hyperparameter set, the model is fitted on six inner training storms and validated on the remaining inner validation storm. This process is repeated for all seven possible choices of the inner validation storm, and the validation scores are averaged across the inner folds. The validation scores are specific to the model class and the vulnerability module component: for the chance-of-loss model, the GAM and XGB minimised the binary log-loss; for the conditional-vulnerability model, the GAM minimised the beta log-loss and the XGB minimised the root mean squared error. The hyperparameter set with the best average validation score is used to refit the model on all seven outer training storms, after which this model is evaluated on the outer held-out storm. Hence, the outer held-out winter storm is not used for model selection or model fitting and is used only once for final evaluation. This nested structure ensures that hyperparameter tuning and model fitting are not influenced by the outer held-out winter storm, providing clean prediction performance results for unseen winter storms.

The outlier storm of 18-01-2018 is not included in the nested leave-one-storm-out cross-validation framework, because it is reserved as an external extrapolation test.

Figure 6. Leave-one-storm-out cross-validation framework. This figure depicts a schematic overview of the nested leave-one-storm-out cross-validation framework. Each WS_s denotes all observations associated with winter storm s . In the outer LOSO loop (on the left), one winter storm is held out as the test storm (in orange), while the remaining seven storms form the outer training set (in grey). Hyperparameter tuning is performed within this outer training set using an inner LOSO procedure (on the right). The inner loop is shown for the example in which WS_1 is held out as the outer test storm: one of the remaining storms is used as the inner validation storm (in blue), and the other six storms are used for training (in grey). After hyperparameter selection, the model is refitted on all seven outer training storms and evaluated on the outer held-out test storm.

Aggregation and out-of-sample evaluation metrics

For the chance-of-loss model (COLM), the predicted number of damaged residential buildings in winter storm s is

$$\hat{P}_s^{COLM} = \sum_i \hat{p}_{is}$$

and the observed number of damaged residential buildings in winter storm s is

$$O_s^{COLM} = \sum_i Z_{is}$$

For the conditional-vulnerability model (CVM), the predicted aggregate residential building damage (of the damaged buildings) in winter storm s is

$$\hat{P}_s^{CVM} = \sum_{i:Z_{is}=1} \hat{v}_{is} R_i$$

and the observed aggregate residential building damage (of the damaged buildings) in winter storm s is

$$O_s^{CVM} = \sum_{i:Z_{is}=1} D_{is}$$

The aggregate expected damage (ED) in winter storm s is

$$\hat{P}_s^{ED} = \sum_i \hat{p}_{is} \hat{v}_{is} R_i$$

and the observed aggregate residential building damage in winter storm s is

$$O_s^{ED} = \sum_i D_{is}$$

Note that the O_s^{CVM} and O_s^{ED} are numerically equal; we retain separate labels only to align the observed values with the CVM and ED prediction targets.

The MBE measures aggregate bias across winter storms, whereas the MAPE measures event-level predictive accuracy. For each target $m \in \{COL, CVM, ED\}$, the estimated percentage difference between the predicted and observed totals across all winter storms is calculated as

$$\widehat{MBE}^m = 100 \times \frac{\sum_s \hat{P}_s^m - \sum_s O_s^m}{\sum_s O_s^m}$$

and the estimated average absolute winter-storm level percentage error is calculated as

$$\widehat{MAPE}^m = \frac{1}{S} \sum_s \left| 100 \times \frac{\hat{P}_s^m - O_s^m}{O_s^m} \right|$$

where S is the number of held-out winter storms.

Calibration curves and residual diagnostics

To complement the aggregate evaluation metrics, insured-object-level diagnostics are reported for the model specification with wind gusts, building characteristics and location effects, which is the best-performing expected damage feature set. The diagnostics are based on out-of-fold predictions from the outer leave-one-storm-out cross-validation. For chance of loss, we create calibration curves by grouping observations into 100 quantile bins by predicted chance of loss, and compare the mean predicted chance of loss with the observed fraction of damaged residential buildings in each bin. For conditional damage ratio, we create prediction residuals using the observations with damage. We define the conditional damage ratio residual as observed conditional damage ratio minus predicted conditional damage ratio, and summarise the residual pattern over the prediction range using a LOWESS smooth. These diagnostics assess insured-object-level calibration and residual structure, whereas MBE and MAPE evaluate aggregate bias and storm-level predictive accuracy. The calibration curves for the chance of loss predictions and the residual diagnostics for the conditional damage ratio predictions can be found in Supplementary Figures S1 and S2, respectively.

Supplement

S1 Filtering the damage data

The insurance dataset provides weather-related residential building claims and policyholder information in the Netherlands. As the Dutch financial conglomerate insures a wide range of environmental- and weather-related damage to residential buildings, additional filters need to be applied in order to isolate claims resulting from winter storms. Accordingly, residential building claims caused by earthquakes, floods, lightning, meteorite impacts and frost are excluded from the sample.

S2 Calculating reconstruction values

The reconstruction values of the residential buildings are calculated according to best practices in the Dutch insurance industry. This methodology is specifically designed for residential buildings and provided by the Dutch Association of Insurers (Verbond van Verzekeraars, 2025). The reconstruction value represents the cost of rebuilding a residential building according to the latest building codes, in case the building is damaged completely. It therefore excludes any value derived from a building's location or the land it is placed on. The reconstruction value is approximated by multiplying a building's volume (m^3) with a predetermined price which is tailored to the building's type, the construction year and characteristics of the building's structures. The baseline prices range from €740 per m^3 building volume for terraced houses built after 2015, to €1,040 per m^3 building volume for detached houses built before and after 2015. The methodology distinguishes six building types: terraced houses, corner houses, semi-detached houses, detached houses, apartments situated up to and including the fourth floor, and apartments situated between the fifth and up to and including the eighth floor. There are two construction year categories: before and after 2015. Premiums and discounts can be applied to the baseline building volume prices to reflect characteristics of the building's structures which are of further influence to the reconstruction value. Among others, these structures include the foundation, the roof, the exterior walls, solar panels and heat generation installations. The reader is referred to the latest version of the reconstruction value calculation manual of the Dutch Association of Insurers (called *Herbouwwaardemeter Woningen 2025*) for an overview of all building volume prices and optional price corrections (Verbond van Verzekeraars, 2025).

S3 Indexing the ground-up damage and reconstruction values

The ground-up damage and reconstruction values are denoted in 2025 price levels. To adjust the price levels at which the damage data were originally recorded, a price index was derived from the development of the reconstruction value prices in the aforementioned methodology of the Dutch Association of Insurers. Table S1 contains this price index for the years 2015-2025, with 2015 set as the reference year. The price index was constructed by taking the weighted average of the baseline volume prices of all building types, where the share of a particular building type in the total building stock served as its weight. The development of this weighted average building volume price in turn determined the evolution of the price index. The share of a particular building type in the total building stock was based on building stock information provided by the Central Agency for Statistics of the Netherlands (Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek [CBS], 2023). Table S2 provides the allocated weights (i.e. shares in the total building stock) per building type, which were assumed to stay fixed over the period of interest.

Table S1. Price index

Year	Price Index
2015	100
2016	107
2017	108
2018	110
2019	113
2020	127
2021	130
2022	141
2023	157
2024	162
2025	168

This table provides the price index which was used to adjust the price levels of the ground-up damage and reconstruction values.

Table S2. Building type weights

Building type	Share in building stock
Terraced & Corner houses	42%
Semi-detached houses	9%
Detached houses	13%
Apartments, floor 0 to 4	18%
Apartments, floor 5 to 8	18%

This table provides the weights which were used in the price index calculation.

S4 XGBoost hyperparameter search space

Table S3. XGBoost hyperparameter search space. Candidate values and fixed settings used in the inner leave-one-storm-out cross-validation for both the chance-of-loss and conditional-vulnerability models. Single-value entries were held fixed; multi-value entries were searched over the listed grid.

Hyperparameter	Search space or fixed value	Role in XGBoost
n_estimators	[1000, 2000]	Number of boosting rounds
learning_rate	[0.01]	Step-size shrinkage applied to each boosting round
max_depth	[3, 7]	Maximum depth of each tree
min_child_weight	[1]	Minimum child-node weight
subsample	[0.75]	Row subsampling fraction per tree
colsample_bytree	[0.75]	Feature subsampling fraction per tree
gamma	[0]	Minimum loss reduction required for an additional split
reg_alpha	[0, 1]	L1 regularisation strength
reg_lambda	[0, 1]	L2 regularisation strength
max_bin	[256]	Maximum number of histogram bins

Figure S1. Out-of-sample calibration curves for the chance-of-loss models. The figure shows insured-object-level calibration curves for the GLM, GAM and XGB chance-of-loss models using the specification with wind gusts, building characteristics and location effects. The insured-object-level predictions are out-of-fold predictions from the outer leave-one-storm-out cross-validation. In the upper panels, observations are grouped into 100 quantile bins of predicted chance of loss. The blue line plots, for each bin, the mean predicted chance of loss against the observed chance of loss, defined as the fraction of damaged residential buildings in that bin. The grey dashed diagonal denotes perfect calibration; blue curves below this line indicate overprediction and blue curves above it indicate underprediction. The blue curves remain close to the perfect-calibration line over most of the prediction range, indicating good overall insured-object-level calibration, but the upper tail is overpredicted, especially for XGB. In the lower panels, histograms show the density distribution of insured-object-level chance of loss predictions; the vertical dashed line denotes the mean of the predictions. Across the 8,321,040 policy-storm observations, 24,374 damaged residential buildings were observed, corresponding to an observed chance of loss of 0.293%. The mean predicted chance of loss was slightly lower for all model classes: 0.288% for GLM, 0.287% for GAM and 0.285% for XGB, equivalent to 23,994, 23,870 and 23,714 predicted damaged residential buildings, respectively.

Figure S2. Out-of-sample residual diagnostics for the conditional-vulnerability models. The figure shows insured-object-level residual diagnostics for the GLM, GAM and XGB conditional-vulnerability models using the specification with wind gusts, building characteristics and location effects. The insured-object-level predictions are out-of-fold predictions from the outer leave-one-storm-out cross-validation. In the upper panels each point represents one damaged residential building, and depicts the conditional damage ratio residual against the predicted conditional damage ratio. The residual is defined as observed conditional damage ratio minus predicted conditional damage ratio; positive residuals indicate underprediction and negative residuals indicate overprediction. The grey dashed horizontal line denotes a zero residual, and the red line shows a LOWESS smooth of the mean residual. A well-centred conditional-vulnerability model should have a smooth residual curve close to zero across the prediction range. The LOWESS curves remain close to zero over most of the prediction range, although the GLM and GAM smooths turn positive at the highest predicted conditional damage ratios, indicating underprediction in this upper tail. In the lower panels, histograms show the density distribution of predicted conditional damage ratios; the vertical dashed line denotes the mean prediction. Across the 24,374 damaged residential buildings, the mean observed conditional damage ratio was 0.510%. The mean predicted conditional damage ratios are 0.520% for GLM, 0.519% for GAM and 0.514% for XGB, corresponding to mean residuals of -0.010 , -0.009 , and -0.004 percentage points, respectively.

Figure S3. GLM chance-of-loss model for the model specification with wind gusts, building characteristics and location effects. Continuous-feature panels show linear term contributions, while the intercept and categorical-feature panels show coefficient estimates. Effects are displayed on the model scale, corresponding to the log-odds of the chance of loss rather than the predicted chance of loss scale. Consequently, linear effects on this model scale can translate into non-linear relationships after transformation to predicted chance of loss through the inverse-logit link. Location effects are not displayed. Coloured estimates correspond to fits with the indicated winter storm held out, and black estimates correspond to the full-sample fit. Grey distributions show the empirical distributions of the continuous predictors.

Figure S4. GLM conditional-vulnerability model for the model specification with wind gusts, building characteristics and location effects. Continuous-feature panels show linear term contributions, while the intercept and categorical-feature panels show coefficient estimates. Effects are displayed on the model scale, corresponding to the logit of the conditional damage ratio rather than the predicted conditional damage ratio scale. Consequently, linear effects on this model scale can translate into non-linear relationships after transformation to predicted conditional damage ratios through the inverse-logit link. Location effects are not displayed. Coloured estimates correspond to fits with the indicated winter storm held out, and black estimates correspond to the full-sample fit. Grey distributions show the empirical distributions of the continuous predictors.

Figure S5. GAM chance-of-loss model for the model specification with wind gusts, building characteristics and location effects. Continuous-feature panels show smooth partial effects, while the intercept and categorical-feature panels show coefficient estimates. Effects are displayed on the model scale, corresponding to the log-odds of the chance of loss rather than the predicted chance of loss scale. Consequently, linear effects on this model scale can translate into non-linear relationships after transformation to predicted chance of loss through the inverse-logit link. Location effects are not displayed. Coloured estimates correspond to fits with the indicated winter storm held out, and black estimates correspond to the full-sample fit. Smooths are centred at the common anchor, defined as the median full-sample value within the overlapping support; curves outside each training support are omitted. Grey distributions show the empirical distributions of the continuous predictors.

Figure S6. GAM conditional-vulnerability model for the model specification with wind gusts, building characteristics and location effects. Continuous-feature panels show smooth partial effects, while the intercept and categorical-feature panels show coefficient estimates. Effects are displayed on the model scale, corresponding to the logit of the conditional damage ratio rather than the predicted conditional damage ratio scale. Consequently, linear effects on this model scale can translate into non-linear relationships after transformation to predicted conditional damage ratios through the inverse-logit link. Location effects are not displayed. Coloured estimates correspond to fits with the indicated winter storm held out, and black estimates correspond to the full-sample fit. Smooths are centred at the common anchor, defined as the median full-sample value within the overlapping support; curves outside each training support are omitted. Grey distributions show the empirical distributions of the continuous predictors.

Figure S7. Global SHAP feature importance and local SHAP beeswarm summary for the XGB chance-of-loss model fitted on all eight cross-validation storms and with the wind gust, building characteristics and location effects specification. The upper panel shows global feature importance, measured as the mean absolute feature SHAP value. The lower panel shows a SHAP beeswarm summary of local SHAP values for the continuous features. Each point represents one observation included in the SHAP calculation; the horizontal position gives the signed SHAP contribution to the model output, and colour denotes the corresponding feature value from low to high. Positive SHAP values increase the model output relative to the model baseline and negative values decrease it. SHAP values are on the log-odds scale.

Figure S8. Global SHAP feature importance and local SHAP beeswarm summary for the XGB conditional-vulnerability model fitted on all eight cross-validation storms and with the wind gust, building characteristics and location effects specification. The upper panel shows global feature importance, measured as the mean absolute feature SHAP value. The lower panel shows a SHAP beeswarm summary of local SHAP values for the continuous features. Each point represents one observation included in the SHAP calculation; the horizontal position gives the signed SHAP contribution to the model output, and colour denotes the corresponding feature value from low to high. Positive SHAP values increase the model output relative to the model baseline and negative values decrease it. SHAP values are on the logit scale.

Figure S9. Chance of loss predictions by model class and held-out winter storm. Predicted chance of loss as a function of maximum wind gust for the GLM, GAM and XGB chance-of-loss models. Predictions are shown for models fitted with each winter storm held out and for the full-sample fit, using the wind gust, building characteristics, and location effects specification. Predictions are evaluated over wind gust speed while holding all other features fixed at their mean values for continuous variables and most frequently observed values for categorical variables. The dashed vertical line marks the out-of-sample boundary at 35 m/s; the grey shaded area marks wind gust speeds above that boundary.

Figure S10. Conditional damage ratio predictions by model class and held-out winter storm. Predicted conditional damage ratio as a function of maximum wind gust for the GLM, GAM and XGB conditional-vulnerability models. Predictions are shown for models fitted with each winter storm held out and for the full-sample fit, using the wind gust, building characteristics, and location effects specification. Predictions are evaluated over wind gust speed while holding all other features fixed at their mean values for continuous variables and most frequently observed values for categorical variables. The dashed vertical line marks the out-of-sample boundary at 35 m/s; the grey shaded area marks wind gust speeds above that boundary.

Figure S11. XGB SHAP main-effect and pairwise-interaction matrix for the chance-of-loss model. The heatmap is based on exact SHAP interaction values from the XGB chance-of-loss model fitted on all eight cross-validation storms and with the wind gust, building characteristics and location effects specification. Diagonal cells show the mean absolute SHAP main effect for each feature. Off-diagonal cells show the mean absolute full pairwise SHAP interaction effect between features, calculated as twice the mean absolute off-diagonal SHAP interaction value because the pairwise interaction is split symmetrically between the two features. Cell shading and in-cell numbers refer to the same metric. All values are on the log-odds scale.

Figure S12. XGB SHAP main-effect and pairwise-interaction matrix for the conditional-vulnerability model. The heatmap is based on exact SHAP interaction values from the XGB conditional-vulnerability model fitted on all eight cross-validation storms and with the wind gust, building characteristics and location effects specification. Diagonal cells show the mean absolute SHAP main effect for each feature. Off-diagonal cells show the mean absolute full pairwise SHAP interaction effect between features, calculated as twice the mean absolute off-diagonal SHAP interaction value because the pairwise interaction is split symmetrically between the two features. Cell shading and in-cell numbers refer to the same metric. All values are on the logit scale.

Table S4. Out-of-sample performance of the expected damage predictions per storm. Reported values denote storm-level prediction errors for expected damage, calculated as percentage differences between aggregate model predictions and observations; positive values indicate overprediction and negative values indicate underprediction. The final columns report the signed mean bias error (MBE), defined as the percentage difference between total predicted and total observed damage across all winter storms and the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), defined as the average absolute storm-level percentage error. The model specification abbreviations are: W for maximum wind gust; B for building characteristics; L for two-digit postal code location effects; P24 for 24-hour precipitation; TSm for daily mean of the thermodynamic state variables; and TSd for daily changes in the thermodynamic state variables. IO is the intercept-only benchmark.

Winter storm	All	10-2-2020	23-2-2020	16-2-2020	11-3-2021	23-2-2017	3-1-2018	10-3-2019	9-2-2020		
Buildings in portfolio	8,321,040	1,029,029	1,029,098	1,029,050	1,024,003	1,072,383	1,068,280	1,040,244	1,028,953		
Damaged buildings	24,374	1,379	1,746	2,225	2,451	3,210	3,393	3,921	6,049		
Observed damage	€ 50,498,017	€2,359,111	€2,828,088	€4,969,277	€4,787,204	€6,676,547	€7,882,052	€9,386,094	€11,609,644		
Model class	Model specification									MBE	MAPE
	IO	187.95%	135.81%	30.00%	32.74%	-4.14%	-21.27%	-36.70%	-52.97%	-0.42%	62.70%
GLM	W	83.30%	107.28%	10.76%	34.57%	-5.69%	-13.69%	-54.59%	-11.00%	-1.33%	40.11%
	W + B	87.69%	112.46%	14.38%	38.70%	-4.29%	-10.77%	-53.81%	-6.59%	1.71%	41.09%
	W + B + L	69.27%	105.44%	13.35%	25.83%	-9.19%	-16.49%	-50.89%	8.07%	1.51%	37.32%
	W + B + L + P24	74.98%	138.36%	13.12%	33.40%	-9.00%	-16.36%	-51.21%	7.95%	4.27%	43.05%
	W + B + L + P24 + TSm	124.60%	210.66%	-34.72%	32.32%	-2.05%	-8.45%	-61.61%	-2.62%	3.62%	59.63%
	W + B + L + P24 + TSd	101.77%	152.36%	15.66%	6.32%	1.86%	-34.09%	-51.01%	248.78%	58.07%	76.48%
GAM	W	76.12%	107.99%	14.67%	34.60%	-4.72%	-12.64%	-54.81%	-19.34%	-2.90%	40.61%
	W + B	87.83%	117.27%	21.87%	39.77%	-4.00%	-8.57%	-54.12%	-13.68%	1.52%	43.39%
	W + B + L	79.15%	106.67%	15.74%	27.87%	-9.60%	-15.17%	-46.94%	-1.22%	1.22%	37.79%
	W + B + L + P24	72.41%	104.72%	29.47%	9.39%	-5.99%	-14.87%	-53.65%	-12.24%	-2.86%	37.84%
	W + B + L + P24 + TSm	144.73%	221.81%	3.78%	42.06%	-6.61%	-9.65%	-56.34%	-10.19%	8.35%	61.90%
	W + B + L + P24 + TSd	109.82%	140.54%	46.28%	17.69%	7.03%	-28.90%	-55.41%	-85.71%	-14.35%	61.42%
XGB	W	72.61%	109.14%	18.22%	30.83%	-7.03%	-12.30%	-52.48%	-18.63%	-2.67%	40.16%
	W + B	75.44%	113.28%	22.87%	34.98%	-7.22%	-9.26%	-50.41%	-13.32%	0.60%	40.85%
	W + B + L	75.43%	101.61%	22.75%	23.93%	-11.43%	-16.83%	-47.12%	-2.60%	0.23%	37.71%
	W + B + L + P24	83.05%	85.45%	44.27%	6.29%	-8.78%	-17.78%	-46.42%	-17.10%	-2.88%	38.64%
	W + B + L + P24 + TSm	245.17%	763.37%	53.98%	35.48%	-11.91%	-20.19%	-71.05%	-38.16%	36.18%	154.91%
	W + B + L + P24 + TSd	57.03%	158.64%	7.82%	0.46%	17.87%	-17.25%	-45.42%	-36.56%	-4.81%	42.63%

Table S5. Out-of-sample chance-of-loss model performance per storm. Reported values denote storm-level prediction errors for the predicted number of damaged residential buildings, calculated as percentage differences between aggregate model predictions and observations; positive values indicate overprediction and negative values indicate underprediction. The final columns report the signed mean bias error (MBE), defined as the percentage difference between the total predicted and total observed number of damaged residential buildings across all winter storms, and the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), defined as the average absolute storm-level percentage error in the predicted number of damaged residential buildings. The model specification abbreviations are: W for maximum wind gust; B for building characteristics; L for two-digit postal code location effects; P24 for 24-hour precipitation; TSm for daily mean of the thermodynamic state variables; and TSd for daily changes in the thermodynamic state variables. IO is the intercept-only benchmark.

Winter storm Buildings in portfolio	All	10-2-2020	23-2-2020	16-2-2020	11-3-2021	23-2-2017	3-1-2018	10-3-2019	9-2-2020		
		Observed damaged buildings	1,029,029	1,029,098	1,029,050	1,024,003	1,072,383	1,068,280	1,040,244	1,028,953	MBE
	8,321,040										
	24,374	1,379	1,746	2,225	2,451	3,210	3,393	3,921	6,049		
Model class	Model specification									MBE	MAPE
	IO	135.31%	82.90%	40.48%	25.52%	-2.46%	-8.92%	-25.47%	-57.25%	-0.02%	47.29%
GLM	W	52.88%	64.64%	20.89%	30.56%	-2.09%	0.42%	-47.04%	-23.74%	-1.07%	30.28%
	W + B	51.79%	62.74%	21.31%	30.02%	-4.00%	0.15%	-46.75%	-21.61%	-1.00%	29.79%
	W + B + L	35.07%	56.36%	19.51%	18.98%	-8.78%	-5.62%	-44.18%	-8.95%	-1.56%	24.68%
	W + B + L + P24	35.68%	84.50%	20.03%	21.39%	-8.77%	-5.10%	-44.33%	-8.94%	0.84%	28.59%
	W + B + L + P24 + TSm	60.11%	138.11%	-21.97%	21.68%	0.65%	3.06%	-54.08%	-16.36%	1.22%	39.50%
	W + B + L + P24 + TSd	53.90%	91.16%	20.85%	-5.10%	0.61%	-23.36%	-44.76%	134.63%	34.01%	46.80%
GAM	W	47.33%	65.04%	24.51%	30.54%	-0.78%	1.72%	-46.82%	-30.83%	-2.40%	30.94%
	W + B	51.34%	64.84%	26.29%	30.00%	-4.97%	1.15%	-46.56%	-27.81%	-1.92%	31.62%
	W + B + L	44.39%	56.18%	21.71%	19.95%	-9.91%	-5.39%	-38.99%	-17.19%	-2.07%	26.71%
	W + B + L + P24	34.07%	62.74%	33.47%	2.98%	-6.80%	-4.96%	-46.56%	-26.19%	-5.80%	27.22%
	W + B + L + P24 + TSm	75.47%	144.88%	21.71%	33.52%	-3.72%	0.09%	-46.56%	-23.49%	6.20%	43.68%
	W + B + L + P24 + TSd	61.46%	81.47%	55.76%	10.52%	2.13%	-19.23%	-48.56%	-88.85%	-16.80%	46.00%
XGB	W	45.98%	67.74%	27.94%	28.40%	-1.84%	2.87%	-44.92%	-30.58%	-1.80%	31.28%
	W + B	43.28%	63.67%	27.48%	26.73%	-6.75%	0.18%	-43.74%	-28.20%	-2.69%	30.00%
	W + B + L	42.98%	55.94%	27.43%	18.19%	-10.03%	-6.24%	-40.70%	-19.12%	-2.71%	27.58%
	W + B + L + P24	41.67%	50.83%	47.60%	0.91%	-6.04%	-5.48%	-40.10%	-29.45%	-4.88%	27.76%
	W + B + L + P24 + TSm	118.64%	548.66%	66.27%	29.26%	-7.36%	-9.56%	-62.63%	-45.47%	31.35%	110.98%
	W + B + L + P24 + TSd	19.98%	97.71%	11.76%	-11.97%	20.98%	-0.32%	-39.95%	-46.36%	-7.22%	31.13%

Table S6. Out-of-sample conditional-vulnerability model performance per storm. The conditional-vulnerability model is evaluated on observations with damage, and in terms of damage rather than damage ratio, with damage computed as the predicted damage ratio multiplied by the associated reconstruction value. Reported values denote storm-level prediction errors for conditional damage, calculated as percentage differences between aggregate model predictions and observations; positive values indicate overprediction and negative values indicate underprediction. The final columns report the signed mean bias error (MBE), defined as the percentage difference between total predicted and total observed conditional damage across all winter storms, and the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), defined as the average absolute storm-level percentage error in conditional damage. The model specification abbreviations are: W for maximum wind gust; B for building characteristics; L for two-digit postal code location effects; P24 for 24-hour precipitation; TSm for daily mean of the thermodynamic state variables; and TSd for daily changes in the thermodynamic state variables. IO is the intercept-only benchmark.

Winter storm	Total	10-2-2020	23-2-2020	16-2-2020	11-3-2021	23-2-2017	3-1-2018	10-3-2019	9-2-2020		
Observed damaged buildings	24,374	1,379	1,746	2,225	2,451	3,210	3,393	3,921	6,049		
Observed damage	€50,498,017	€2,359,111	€2,828,088	€4,969,277	€4,787,204	€6,676,547	€7,882,052	€9,386,094	€11,609,644		
Model class	Model specification									MBE	MAPE
	IO	40.95%	30.21%	3.35%	11.90%	8.75%	-6.43%	3.40%	22.46%	11.01%	15.93%
GLM	W	38.32%	30.34%	2.54%	12.56%	8.66%	-6.10%	4.68%	31.44%	13.22%	16.83%
	W + B	27.29%	25.73%	-4.14%	5.89%	0.83%	-12.08%	-6.41%	20.50%	4.61%	12.86%
	W + B + L	26.90%	25.64%	-4.41%	5.78%	0.13%	-12.29%	-6.20%	20.12%	4.38%	12.68%
	W + B + L + P24	30.96%	23.77%	-5.07%	10.12%	0.20%	-12.47%	-6.26%	19.67%	4.68%	13.57%
	W + B + L + P24 + TSm	42.17%	25.81%	-15.68%	8.98%	-2.22%	-12.19%	-10.37%	18.05%	2.75%	16.93%
	W + B + L + P24 + TSd	31.82%	27.18%	-4.69%	12.10%	1.78%	-14.29%	-3.96%	50.38%	12.55%	18.27%
GAM	W	37.81%	30.26%	3.11%	12.63%	8.64%	-6.04%	4.92%	30.41%	13.07%	16.73%
	W + B	26.04%	24.37%	-4.12%	5.64%	1.12%	-11.93%	-7.09%	18.84%	4.01%	12.40%
	W + B + L	25.86%	24.17%	-4.34%	5.37%	0.23%	-12.27%	-6.86%	18.51%	3.74%	12.20%
	W + B + L + P24	29.64%	18.71%	-3.46%	3.18%	1.55%	-12.08%	-5.70%	18.74%	3.96%	11.63%
	W + B + L + P24 + TSm	42.38%	25.32%	-14.34%	4.52%	-3.01%	-12.17%	-11.20%	18.45%	2.28%	16.42%
	W + B + L + P24 + TSd	30.80%	26.03%	-7.35%	5.23%	5.89%	-13.03%	-3.00%	27.67%	7.22%	14.88%
XGB	W	36.10%	28.43%	3.64%	10.94%	6.54%	-6.42%	5.88%	30.58%	12.66%	16.07%
	W + B	25.71%	21.67%	-3.98%	2.51%	-1.09%	-12.60%	-5.18%	18.89%	3.53%	11.45%
	W + B + L	24.58%	21.93%	-4.12%	1.88%	-0.96%	-13.34%	-5.75%	17.66%	2.93%	11.28%
	W + B + L + P24	31.87%	17.13%	-3.42%	-0.77%	-1.24%	-14.52%	-3.89%	16.23%	2.62%	11.13%
	W + B + L + P24 + TSm	60.88%	28.54%	-5.59%	0.53%	-4.94%	-14.55%	-13.78%	15.83%	2.10%	18.08%
	W + B + L + P24 + TSd	36.87%	25.32%	-5.03%	12.83%	-2.83%	-17.18%	3.15%	18.36%	5.61%	15.20%

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